

Streamlining FPGA Circuit Design and Verification with Python and *py4hw*

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Abstract—Classic hardware design languages, such as VHDL and Verilog, were born more than 30 years ago to improve the productivity of circuit design offered by manual schematic drawing. Over the years, the effort of Digital Hardware Design has shifted from circuit design to circuit verification. Although classic HDLs have been extended to adapt to this changing scenario, they have a hard time to cope with the complexity demanded at the design and verification stages. Radical changes incorporating high-level software programming languages in the design and verification processes seem inevitable. Accordingly, many new HDL proposals are already based on Python. In this paper, we present a novel Python-based HDL framework that tries to address some of the limitations of current Python-based HDLs with a special focus on verification and education.

Index Terms—FPGA, Verilog, Python

I. INTRODUCTION

The Python programming language has become very popular in the scientific community due to its simplicity, cross-platform support, easy learning curve, and a multitude of existing and ever-increasing functionality that is easily distributed through Internet-based setup infrastructures like PyPi and Conda. Hardware design languages (HDLs) like VHDL and Verilog were born as domain-specific languages to address the productivity limitations of manual schematic drawing. Modern digital circuits are generally designed using a compositional methodology, where circuits are subdivided into simpler interconnected blocks. This division is repeated until simple enough circuits, which are part of the platform primitives, are obtained.

The benefit of using a domain-specific language was justified when Object-Oriented (OO) languages were not mainstream, and it was not easy to express the compositional structure of hardware with them. Now, General-Purpose Programming Languages (GPPLs) can easily describe complex circuit descriptions by instantiating smaller blocks. The evolution of HDLs has moved the attention to the circuit verification features of the languages. We argue that, instead of trying to transform the domain-specific HDLs into GPPLs, it makes more sense to complement existing GPPLs to be able to describe Hardware blocks and provide a simulation infrastructure that allows complex verification. Several proposals have followed this approach. To name a few: SystemC [1] based on C/C++, JHDL [2] based on Java, and Chisel [3] based on Scala. We believe that some roadblocks hinder their

wide adoption. While Java is still popular in the business domain, it is not so popular among the scientific and electrical engineering communities. Also, even with the relative success of Chisel, Scala is not a very popular language. On the other hand, while C/C++ is very popular in the scientific and electrical engineering communities, the language suffers from some limitations (e.g. poor introspection) that makes it less attractive to become the center of an HDL framework.

Despite the well-known performance limitations, Python still offers some compelling features to be the base of an HDL framework. There have been several proposals based on Python in the literature [4]–[9], but, they lack some features like visualization, interactive simulation, and, in some cases, they have an unclear separation between hardware design styles. These features are part of our proposed framework *py4hw* and could be incorporated into some of the other Python-based tools. As part of our commitment to the Open Hardware movement [10] and to improve education in Digital Hardware Design, we have made our tools available on both GitHub and PyPI under the GPL 3.0 license. We believe in the importance of open access to tools and resources for the advancement of the field, and we hope that our contributions will support the broader community of hardware designers and educators.

The organization of the paper is as follows: In Section II, we describe the main aspects of the *py4hw* framework. Special focus is given to the flexibility aspects of the framework in Section III and the visualization features in Section IV. Section V details the verification features of the framework. We describe the strength of the framework for education in section VI. Before concluding, Section VII analyzes related work and compares it with the current proposal.

II. *py4hw*

The functionality base of Python is far superior to that available in Verilog/SystemVerilog. Hence, using Python in *py4hw* provides an excellent foundation for elaborating complex hardware, defining of simulation stimuli, and developing verification testbenches. *py4hw* is specially optimized for the design of synchronous digital circuits, and it is influenced by JHDL [2].

The evolution of hardware design has consolidated three main design styles:

- Structural: description of blocs and their connections
- Register transfer level (RTL): description of the response of circuits at certain events (signal activation or clock edge)
- Sequential: Description of processes using a Von-Neumann-like approach where actions occur by the execution of an algorithm

Many Python-based HDLs mix design styles (as Chisel also does) or use non-intuitive methods to create hardware circuits, introducing unnecessary confusion to the designer. *py4hw* aims to differentiate between design styles and avoid language constraints that limit the freedom to create any circuit.

py4hw follows and Object Oriented (OO) design style. Every circuit (equivalent to Verilog module) is modeled by a Python class, which can be instantiated by other circuits. In Verilog, modules have two different sets of constructor-arguments, a mandatory set for the input and output wires, and an optional set for module parameters. In *py4hw*, the only mandatory constructor-arguments are the parent circuit and the name of the instance. *py4hw* maintains a hierarchical object model with parent-child relations. Each circuit instance contains a link to its parent, and a dictionary of children indexed by instance name. The top-level entity of the hierarchy is the `HWSystem` object. Thus, circuit constructors can have an arbitrary number of additional parameters, and the interface of the circuit (inputs and outputs) is built during runtime avoiding any static interface definition. The clock is implicit. All circuits have an assigned clock driver which is normally inherited from the parent circuit. However, multiple clock-drivers can be used, and there is support for gated clocks by using a special clock-driver object.

A fundamental class is the `Wire` class. An instance of the `Wire` class represents a signal that connects one source with one-or-more sinks. Wires have a width, a name, and a parent circuit that must be specified during creation. A significant difference with other HDLs is that wires are indivisible. Extracting specific bits from a wire, concatenating wires, or obtaining a range of wires from a wire require to use specific circuits. All circuits inherit from the class `Logic`, which provides some basic methods to create the circuit interface. Structural, RTL, and sequential design styles are supported in *py4hw*. The structural design style is based on the instantiation of objects from previously defined classes in the constructor of the class. The following code illustrates how to design a 1-bit Full Adder circuit with a structural design style.

```
class FullAdder(Logic):
    def __init__(self, parent, name, x, y, ci, s, co):
        super().__init__(parent, name)
        # interface definition
        x = self.addIn('x', x)
        y = self.addIn('y', y)
        ci = self.addIn('ci', ci)
        s = self.addOut('s', s)
        co = self.addOut('co', co)
        # internal wires
        w1 = self.wire('w1', 1)
        w2 = self.wire('w2', 1)
        w3 = self.wire('w3', 1)
        # instances
```

```
Xor2(self, 'g1', x, y, w1)
Xor2(self, 'g2', w1, ci, s)
And2(self, 'g3', w1, ci, w2)
And2(self, 'g4', x, y, w3)
Or2(self, 'g5', w2, w3, co)
```

py4hw also supports RTL design style by allowing to use the behaviour of the circuits using simple Python code. Two possible circuit types are supported: combinational and sequential. In both cases, the constructor of the class is used to define the interface and save their wires into the properties of the object. Combinational behavioral circuits must implement the `propagate` method. The following code illustrates how the previous Full Adder circuit can be described by using a combinational behavioural implementation.

```
class FullAdder(Logic):
    def __init__(self, parent, name, x, y, ci, s, co):
        super().__init__(parent, name)
        # interface definition
        ...

    def propagate(self):
        v = self.x.get() + self.y.get() + self.ci.get()
        self.s.put(v % 2)
        self.co.put(1 if v > 1 else 0)
```

Sequential behavioral circuits are defined by implementing the `clock` method. The following code illustrates how to implement a simple Finite State Machine (FSM) with two states.

```
class FSM(Logic):
    def __init__(self, parent, name, r):
        super().__init__(parent, name)
        self.r = self.addOut('r', r)
        self.state = 0

    def clock(self):
        if (self.state == 0):
            self.r.prepare(1)
            self.state = 1
        elif (self.state == 1):
            self.r.prepare(0)
            self.state = 0
```

Sequential design style can be implemented by combining Python coroutines with the implementation of `clock` method. With this approach, the circuit enters a coroutine on object creation which is automatically blocked after a first `yield` statement is reached. The `clock` method must call the `next` method of the coroutine so that the sequential process advances until the next `yield` statement is found. A similar approach is used in `cocotb` [11] and, from the programmer's perspective, is very similar to SystemC's sequential clocked processes (`SC_CTHREAD`), which used `sc_wait` statement instead of `yield`.

py4hw embeds a cycle-based simulator. The simulator is responsible to propagate the wire values across the circuit and update the state. Using behavioral models instead of structural ones is a known technique to speedup simulation. In the behavioral FullAdder example, the simulator requires a single method invocation to compute the outputs of the circuit. On the other hand, using structural design for the same circuit requires the invocation of the behavioural models of all its hierarchical descendants, which takes more time.

Simulation time can be advanced programmatically. This can be used in combination with state analysis to perform advanced verification and visualization strategies. This strategy was used in [12] to provide a rich visualization of the state of a RISC-V processor while executing an compiled application. Several Python libraries (pylftools, capstone, tkiner, ...) were used to provide a rich user experience.

py4hw generates Verilog from the circuit descriptions. Since the whole circuit hierarchy is maintained in memory, the RTL generation phase only has to traverse the circuit hierarchy and decide which method to apply to generate the equivalent Verilog code for each element of the hierarchy. Structural circuits are directly translated into structural Verilog code. Behaviourally modelled circuits are transpiled into Verilog. Their defining method (either `propagate` or `clock`) is analyzed using introspection to obtain the Abstract Syntax Tree (AST) of the method's source code. Several transformations are applied until the AST can be emitted as a valid Verilog. Calls to external libraries (such as NumPy) can not be used inside behavioural models that are synthesized. On the other hand, there is no restriction to use them on constructors of Structural circuits and behavioral models as simulation stimuli. Using Python's introspection eliminates the need for external libraries that would otherwise be necessary in languages like C/C++ to parse source code.

III. CIRCUIT FLEXIBILITY

The interface of Verilog circuits is fixed by design. This limits the ability to build complex circuits and requires GPLs to assist EDA tools when such flexibility is needed. A often occurs when building a memory-mapped multiplexed bus to communicate a bus-master processor with a flexible number of bus-slave devices. Although the generative Verilog statements could assist in generating the module logic, the inflexibility of the language with respect to the circuit interface prevents the creation of a generic module. A work-around solution could be to design for the worst-case scenario by estimating the maximum number of inputs and leaving wires unconnected. However, this approach can lead to long and error-prone code due to the large number of wires. While SystemVerilog provides some relief with `interface` and `modport` statements, the issue of static interfaces is not fully resolved.

On the contrary, this use-case is extremely simple to implement in *py4hw*. First, because the circuit interface can be created during runtime by using `addIn` and `addOut` methods. Second, because semantically related signals can be grouped in any kind of Python data structure (such as a list, a dictionary, or a specific `Interface` class provided by *py4hw*) and passed to the circuit constructor. The following code illustrates a possible implementation.

```
class MultiplexedBus(Logic):
    def __init__(self, parent, name,
                 master, slaves):
        super().__init__(parent, name)

        self.addInterfaceSink('master', master)
```

```
for i, slave in enumerate(slaves):
    self.addInterfaceSource('slave{}'.format(i),
                           slave.if)

    addr = slave.addr
    ...
```

But interface flexibility is not the only required flexibility. Modern HDLs should also be able to support the manipulation of the circuit. Some intermediate low-level representations (IRs) have been proposed to describe hardware concepts. After the success of the LLVM infrastructure [13] in the Software world, it is expected that Hardware design flows can benefit from an infrastructure that allows the manipulation of the design descriptions in a number of optimization phases. The most relevant IRs are FIRRTL [14] and LLHD [15]. IRs provide a framework where manipulation is possible because in the original context (e.g. Verilog, C/C++, etc.) it was not. However, the in-memory object hierarchy of *py4hw* designs allows the unrestricted manipulation of the system making the IR phase unnecessary. Not all Python-based HDL frameworks support this flexibility. For instance, the MyHDL method to create circuits based on generators is not very adequate to implement this manipulation.

In *py4hw*, the circuit hierarchy can be easily traversed and manipulated, adding or removing ports from a circuit or creating new hardware. As an example, the following Python code manipulates a circuit to insert a `global_enable` signal. The intended goal is that the enable signal of every register found in the circuit hierarchy is controlled by the `global_enable` signal. The code checks whether each register uses the enable signal. If it does not, it adds it and connects it conveniently. Otherwise, it inserts a new `and2` gate combining the former enable signal with the global one. Furthermore, the `global_enable` signal must be included in the interface of all pertinent circuits in the hierarchy.

```
class GlobalEnableInserter:
    i = 0
    def transform(self, obj, gen):
        anyclk = False
        children = set(obj.children.values())

        for child in children:
            if (child.isClockable()):
                if (isinstance(child, Reg)):
                    enable = child.e
                    anyclk = True

            if (enable is None):
                child.addIn('e', gen)
            else:
                name = 'global_ena_{}'.format(self.i)
                self.i += 1
                new_enable = obj.wire(name)
                And2(obj, name, enable, gen, new_enable)
                child.reconnectIn('e', new_enable)

        elif (len(child.children) > 0):
            anyclk |= self.transform(child, gen)

        if (anyclk):
            obj.addIn('global_enable', gen)
            return True
        else:
            return False
```

IV. VISUALIZATION

Circuit visualization is important to understand the structure of a circuit and can be very helpful during validation, as some structural errors can be more easily identified by inspecting diagrams instead of source code. Logic diagrams are extensively used in education, and it is also common practice to use them during the conceptualization of Hardware systems. Since complex circuits are designed in a hierarchical way, visualization tools require to be able to navigate the hierarchy and visualize the connection between all the elements of the system.

FPGA EDA tool manufacturers have included VHDL and Verilog circuit visualization features. However, visualization has to be elaborated by a process that analyzes the whole circuit and the user has little control to automate the generation of such diagrams. Other popular HDLs like Chisel [3], SystemC [1], or MyHDL [4] do not provide any circuit visualization feature.

On the other hand, JHDL [2] had rich visualization features, including interactive simulation with value annotation in the circuit schematic, which was very useful to debug circuit behavior. The HWT Python-based HDL library also includes visualization features.

py4hw has some generic goals regarding the visualization of circuits:

- Any part of the circuit hierarchy should be visualizable
- Circuit visualization should create a manipulable object hierarchy
- The user/designer should be able to control the details of the visualization process, from algorithmic aspects (like layout algorithms) to low-level details (such as colors and line widths).
- Visualization should allow multiple final targets, such as GUIs, images, or Jupyter Notebooks.

In *py4hw*, visualization is controlled by the `Schematic` class, which implements a circuit layout algorithm from scratch. An schematic diagram works with a circuit element from the hierarchy. It is not necessary to process all the circuit to generate a visualization from a node. The layout algorithm is responsible for placing input ports, child instances, and output ports of the circuit in the drawing canvas and route the connections among them.

The currently supported targets are `matplotlib` and `tkinter` canvas. The `Matplotlib` target is very useful to integrate circuit visualization in jupyter notebooks. Figure 1 depicts how a full adder circuit schematic is rendered in a jupyter notebook. The `tkinter` target is useful to visualize any circuit of the hierarchy in an interactive graphical user interface. This is actually used in the interactive simulation workbench that will be described in the following section.

V. VERIFICATION

Simulation is fundamental for verification. Simulation consist on evaluating how the system evolves over time under controlled conditions. Simulation sessions require a circuit

Fig. 1. Schematic visualization of a combinational circuit in a Jupyter notebook

design under test (DUT), some stimuli to inject to the circuit, and the ability to observe the behaviour of the DUT. A test-bench consists of a combination of these three items.

In Verilog, observability is based on printf-like messages and the generation of VCD trace files that record the activity of circuit wires for later inspection using waveform viewers such as the popular gtkwave tool. With SystemVerilog, additional formal methods like assertions were introduced.

In *py4hw*, stimuli can be created by several means. The most simple way is by using the `Constant` or `Sequence` circuits that allow to specify a constant value or a repetitive sequence of constant values respectively. For slightly more complex stimuli it is recommended to create a stimuli class using a sequential behavioral design style to specify inputs. When higher complexity stimuli is required, behavioural models using coroutines can be the best option.

The observability of wires in *py4hw* can be provided by multiple ways. First, wire information can be collected using the `Waveform` class and later displayed (see figure 2). The `Scope` class provides printf-like message outputs. Printf-like messages can also be embedded into user-defined circuits, either to debug the circuit creation phase in the constructor of structural circuits, or by providing info on the simulation progress on behavioral circuits. However, this approach is only recommended during early debugging phases and it is encouraged that these messages are removed from stable circuits to minimize the verbosity of systems during simulation. Assertions are easily supported either by using exceptions or assert statements.

Fig. 2. Waveform visualization in Jupyter notebook

The simulator embedded in *py4hw* is cycle-based [16]. The simulator has a flattened view of all the primitive behavioral elements of the system. When the simulator is initialized

Fig. 3. Interactive Workbench for a Floating Point adder circuit. We can simulate step by step. Left pane shows the hierarchy of the circuit. The top right pane has the interface of the circuit with the current signal values. The bottom right pane shows the schematic of the circuit.

all the elements are classified either being combinational or sequential. Combinational circuit chains are topologically sorted so that they can be correctly evaluated in sequence. This is possible as no asynchronous loops are allowed. In this way, no event propagation is needed, and circuits are only evaluated once. After evaluating combinational circuits, sequential circuits can be evaluated in any arbitrary order.

In *py4hw*, each wire can have an arbitrary width. In other HDL languages based on Java or C/C++, the wire width is limited by design because the underlying simulation infrastructure is using an integer type (64 bits, typically). This is not the case in Python as integers have arbitrary precision.

Modern design techniques require a systematic verification of all created circuits. In SystemVerilog, much effort was devoted to address complex verification. Moreover, the universal verification methodology (UVM), which is based on these SystemVerilog features, was proposed as a standard for the systematic verification of circuits. While unit testing, system testing, and continuous integration can be relatively new concepts to many Hardware designers, they have been very commonly used in complex software projects. Actually, there are several testing frameworks for Python. In *py4hw* we use `Pytest` to do unit testing. This allows to define systematic testing of all the circuits by using assertions, random stimuli, and equivalence checking.

After a bug is detected by using unit tests or system tests it is necessary to identify the source of the error. This can be done by analyzing waveforms in the classical post-mortem approach. However, an alternative method based on interactive simulation can be more efficient. *py4hw* provides an interactive workbench (see figure 3) in which the user/designer can navigate for the circuit hierarchy and view the circuit structure together with the values of the circuit interface. In addition to these methods custom state visualization can be built to transform the circuit state into a higher-level abstraction so that it is easy to identify.

VI. EDUCATION

Digital circuit design for FPGAs has historically required different tools from several vendors to design, synthesize,

simulate and execute the designs. With the proliferation of Open-Source tools the cost aspect of the problem has been minimized, however, the user/designer still needs several tools to design and verify the circuit. Education at all levels is increasingly promoting self-paced courses and remotely accessible infrastructure. This is challenging in Digital Design courses due to the required infrastructure.

Jupyter notebooks are an effective method to combine documentation with software execution. Its use is being introduced in many engineering courses [17] either as part of self-paced courses or laboratory exercises. There is some consensus among digital design education community that students must visualize the circuits they can design with HDLs to fully understand the implications of their decisions. *py4hw* exercise materials have been prepared to use in a Digital Design Course so that the student can test his ability to create his/her circuits and automatically verify if they fulfill the requirements of the exercise. At the same time, a visualization of the created hardware is presented and the equivalent Verilog code is generated. Moreover, the student can run the exercises with the only requirement of a web browser, as the jupyter notebook using the *py4hw* framework can run on a Binder or Collab remote infrastructure.

VII. RELATED WORK

There are many proposals using Python for Hardware design. In Table I we list some of the most relevant.

MyHDL [4] is one of the first and well-known proposals to use Python for Hardware design. It was created in 2003 and has 858 stars in GitHub. Although it has an active community, the project seems to be losing steam and entering a decay phase as can be observed by the last PyPi release date. One of the drawbacks of MyHDL is that component creation was based on generator functions. Each module is described as a function that creates logic entities that are returned as list of objects. Decorators are used to ease the definition of such functions. Hierarchy was hard to obtain in the initial releases. New releases are moving to an approach where hierarchy is maintained, but the momentum of the framework will make the change slow. PyRTL has a similar issue with its structure, as it opts not to use classes for circuit creation and instead aims to simplify usage by concealing hardware creation details.

According to Github stars, the most popular Python-based frameworks are Migen and its derived Amaranth. Their drawback are that they promote a syntax that simultaneously combines different design styles in the source code, which is (from our experience) a source of confusion for many undergraduate students. Moreover, according to the last PyPi release date, development halted in 2019 for Migen, and 2021 for Amaranth.

The project with the most recent PyPi releases is PyMTL3 [8]. It provides different clear design styles which are annotated with function decorators. It also maintains a hierarchy that allows applying transformations as proposed by IR tools. In addition, it is actively used in hardware design courses at Cornell University and Boston University. An interesting

approach is followed by PyLog [9], which provides automatic deployment in some supported FPGAs. However, the language hides the details of hardware structure making it less useful for education. Moreover, it is not distributed through PyPi. HWT [7] covers many aspects of Hardware design. Its main drawback might be the fragmentation of the functionality in several repositories.

None of the analyzed frameworks provide circuit visualization, except for HWT. HWT has a good visualization tool that can be inserted in Jupyter. It is based on the ELK (Eclipse Layout Kit), which is based on Java and is automatically transpiled in Javascript using GWT. Consequently, none of them provide a GUI for interactive simulation, which is very useful for education.

TABLE I
OPEN SOURCE PYTHON-BASED HDL FRAMEWORKS

Framework	Launched	Last PyPi Release	GitHub Repository	Stars
MyHDL [4]	2003	6/2019	myhdl/myhdl	886
PyRTL [6]	2015	9/2021	UCSBarchlab/PyRTL	173
HWT	2016	7/2021	Nic30/hwt	160
Migen	2019	11/2019	m-labs/migen	987
PyMTL3 [8]	2020	5/2022	pymtl/pymtl3	254
PyLog [9]	2021		hst10/pylog	39
Amaranth	2021	12/2021	amaranth-lang/amaranth	1.1k

In addition to these frameworks there are other related Python-based projects with interesting results. PyVerilog [18], available at PyHDI/Pyverilog is not an HDL framework but it is a library for Verilog analysis providing the ability to parse and manipulate Verilog code.

A very relevant work is cocotb [11], with 1.1k stars in GitHub and a last PyPi release in February 2022. Cocotb focuses on testbench generation from Python to inject stimuli into standard HDL projects. To do so, it basically provides a simulation engine that interacts with external simulators (such as QuestaSim, Verilator, etc) and uses Python coroutines to model stimuli generators.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Classic HDL languages are incorporating features of standard programming languages to cope with the requirements of hardware design and verification. Alternatively, hardware creation with software programming languages might be simpler and opens the door to many new engineers to create Hardware.

Currently, Python is one of the most popular programming languages with a rich ecosystem of tools and libraries and a big developer community. There have been several proposals to use Python for hardware design.

Many of them take a very high-level description approach hiding the details of hardware design. In digital design education courses, it is necessary to be able to control the created hardware with good detail and be always clear about what design style we are using. It is also fundamental to visualize the results as soon and as often as possible. Even if using

high-level synthesis, the transformations must be identifiable and explainable to students.

py4hw tries to address these issues by providing a low-level Python library for the compositional creation of digital circuits, their verification and visualization using modern tools such as interactive GUIs and jupyter notebooks. By eliminating the need for third-party software installations and offering early visualization of designed circuits, students have less entry barriers and iterate faster with digital hardware design.

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